

Attitude of Educationalists on Implications of Value-Void Education in Creating Tunneled Individuals: A Case Study of Elizabeth Holmes and Annie Dookhan

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Abstract

Value-oriented education has been an integral facet of education. The need for value education stems from the social malaise in the society and education, being purposeful in making students responsible citizens, must address such deficiencies in values. This study aims to understand the attitude of student teachers and in-service teachers' towards current education and its value systems and seeks their stand on requiring value-oriented education as they are the major stake holders of direct classroom education experience other than students. The case study of Elizabeth Holmes and Annie Dookhan was used to assess how academically strong individuals end up straying into fraudulent ways. The study was administered using an electronic questionnaire, the frequency range was established using SPSS and indexed to percentage values. The data shed light on the attitude of student teachers and in-service teachers feeling that current education fails to inculcate values and suggested some methods of reform in the value systems of current education.

Keywords: Educational Psychology, Elizabeth Holmes, Annie Dookhan, Value-Oriented Education, Ethical Education

Introduction

Education has been an integral element of society and its individuals. Though on a surface level, education is considered to be a tool to shape one's livelihood and means of income through a profession, in a more profound sense, the term education has a much more vast and more profound purpose. "The purpose of education has always been to everyone, in essence, the same – to give the young the things they need to develop in an orderly, sequential way into members of society"(Dewey, 1934). One of the most consequential purposes of education is to mould individuals into the folds of society, equipping them to contemplate, understand and reproduce the actions and other peripheries of society (Kaya & Akdemir, 2016). Society is a group of people who have similar views and who are aware of and appreciate this similarity and can work together to achieve mutual goals (Giddings 1899). The outlook of a society is not rigid. It is subjected to change on various factors like demographics, occupations, communal practices and other beliefs (Allen 1959). As one of the elemental purposes of education is to mound individuals into the folds of society, owing to the changes in societal outlook, the purpose of education also is refined in certain societies. In other words, education is an artefact of society – what education is, and what it is for, are determined by the society in which it is taking place.

According to (Durkheim 1972), society has a significant impact on people. A collective consciousness, or common understanding and behaviour in the world, is made up of conventions, beliefs, and values held by individuals. Individuals are connected and become socially integrated through collective awareness. This exertion of this conventional system and standards on behalf of society bears benchmarks for every person who tries to become a part of society (Thomson 2001). The eagerness to be accepted into the fold is exemplified by the exertion of standards by the accomplished members of society. Society is found to be a group of people who are linked together by specific relationships or styles of behaviour that distinguish them from others who do not participate in these relationships or who behave differently (Ginsberg, 1936). This earmarking of standards and exclusion of others who are not up to those standards creates a gap of social exclusion. The term “social exclusion” refers to a situation in which people are unable to fully engage in economic, social, political, and cultural life, as well as the process that leads to and sustains such a state (UN, 2016). Participation of sections of people in society may be hampered when individuals lack access to tangible resources such as money, work, land, and housing, or to services like education and health care, which are key foundations of well-being. However, involvement is limited when individuals are unable to express themselves or engage with one another, and when their rights and dignity are not treated with equal respect and protection. Thus, social exclusion includes not just monetary deprivation, but also a loss of agency or influence over critical decisions and emotions of alienation and inferiority. Age, gender, handicap, race, ethnicity, religion, migratory status, financial level, location of residence, sexual orientation and gender identity have all been reasons for social exclusion in practically all countries to varying degrees (UN, 2016). Certain theoretical frameworks suggest that social ostracism thwarts fundamental human needs, including self-concept and threatens the healthy development and well-being of individuals (Baumeister & Leary, 2000; Özyurt, 2018; Williams & Nida, 2011). The growing need to be included within the constitution of the

society, individuals lose healthy development towards the shared goal of individual and the society. This evidence is merely correlational, though, so we cannot be sure which way the influence is working. Research in social stratification has long focused on diverging educational success, both attainment and performance, with the traditional predictor being the socioeconomic background of the family. To make it big and get noticed, people often try to achieve things in a mainstream way and sometimes fail, but the quest to make it to the top leads them to undue and fraudulent methods. In a ‘Perspective in biology and medicine’ paper, James Knight, a professor of psychiatry, described how scientists compromise ethical standards. Knight concentrated on the role played by some scientists’ desire for power and prestige to their ongoing fear and anxiety of failure in his writing before the sensational cases involving Nobel laureates erupted. He observed that this fear and anxiety led even the most accomplished person to ensure success by “hook or crook.” He also reiterates how the relationship between moral development and elite rank might be researched. The continuity of education is crucial since learning is a lifelong process that ends with death. It serves as the cornerstone for the growth of a healthy person and society. If there is a shortage of education in our society, our globe cannot have a bright future. The secret to change is education. It is a crucial tool for helping someone understand their obligations to their families, communities, and country. It enhances one’s capacity to perceive the world and combat wrongdoings including injustice, corruption, and violence, among other things (Leverage, 2022).

A study infers that Education must make students: “as citizens in the adult world, to make informed decisions about complex issues and detect falsehood and bias in the arguments of others.” (Skilbeck, p. 60). Education that does not equip a student to identify the apt path towards the intended goal, sensitivity to other people’s well-being and curb the itch to reach the goal with deceit and fraud, is a failure (Akan & Ataş, 2014; Campbell & Ataş Akdemir, 2016). This research tries to determine the attitude of student-teachers and in-service teachers, the main pillars of the current education system towards the effectiveness of today’s education in

driving ethical values hand-in-hand with other subjects and to assess how education played a role in the case of Annie Dookhan and Elisabeth Holmes.

Background

Case of Elizabeth Holmes

At the age of 19, Holmes launched Theranos just before dropping out of Stanford University in California. She wanted to create a business that sold blood testing directly to customers. She wanted to do away with the bulky needles and blood tubes needed to run conventional diagnostic equipment. She asserted that she had created a device that could do more than 200 tests with just a few drops of blood from a finger prick. More media attention than ever before was given to laboratory diagnoses thanks to the captivating and ambitious Holmes. She garnered world attention and was listed as a top influential person on the planet. She also attracted prominent investors and advisers. Theranos's board of directors now includes former US secretaries of state Henry Kissinger and George Shultz, as well as former US secretaries of defence James Mattis and William Perry. Rupert Murdoch, a media billionaire, and Betsy DeVos' family, a former US education secretary, were among the investors. The Palo Alto, California-based business raised around \$945 million and hired more than 800 people. Additionally, it signed agreements with a few major shops. In 2013, the pharmaceutical retailer Walgreens started installing Theranos "wellness centres" in its Arizona shops, eventually establishing 40 locations. The idea was to make it possible for customers to order a panel of blood tests from a local pharmacist at their convenience using just a few drops of blood. Investors and the general public thought Theranos was analysing the blood samples it received using its cutting-edge machinery. However, the company could only actually execute a limited number of tests on its platform. The remaining samples were run by custom blood testing apparatus created by various businesses. The finger-prick samples had to be diluted to increase their volume to match the requirements of such instruments, and the results turned out to be inaccurate. In 2015, Holmes's con started to unravel. Theranos' flaws were revealed by Wall Street Journal reporter John Carreyrou in a

sensational sequence of news stories after Diamandis called the company out. Holmes was given a two-year suspension from running a medical lab following an investigation by the US Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services. Suing Theranos was Walgreens. The US Securities and Exchange Commission also accused Holmes and former Theranos CEO Sunny Balwani of widespread fraud and suspended Holmes for ten years from holding any public business officer or director positions. On January 3, a federal court in San Jose, California, found Holmes guilty of four of the eleven allegations that the prosecution had levelled against her. These four accusations included three for wire fraud against investors and one for conspiracy to commit wire fraud against investors. Holmes was absolved by the jury on four counts of patient fraud and was found not guilty on three more counts involving investor fraud (Waltz 2022).

Case of Annie Dookhan

No one in the lab put forth more effort than Annie Dookhan, who performed quality control for a manufacturer of vaccines close to Boston. She frequently arrived first thing in the morning and left the last thing at night. She admitted to her colleagues that she had transferred to a state university after quitting Harvard as an undergraduate due to financial difficulties years earlier. All of it was untrue, which was the only problem. Dookhan had never enrolled in a Harvard course, undergraduate or graduate. Harvard didn't even have a part-time chemistry programme. Dookhan had made everything up as a ruse to get promoted. Dookhan, who was then 25 years old, had already lied numerous times about her credentials and past. Even though the institution didn't provide such accolades, she insisted that she had graduated with *Magna cum laude*. She also misrepresented her parents' occupations by saying they were both doctors. She continued to tell these small lies while in college and afterwards at the vaccine manufacturer and state drug lab, where she made up titles for herself. She tested 9,239 drug samples in the first year, which is almost three times more than the average of the other nine scientists. She began to be referred to as "superwoman," which made her sparkle. Although she was in pain on the inside. She married an engineer she had met in

Trinidad in 2004. She became pregnant shortly after. But the first pregnancy terminated in miscarriage, and a second miscarriage followed. Dookhan spent even more time at the lab rather than taking time off to deal. She sped through 11,232 samples, nearly twice as many as the chemist in second place. In the end, Dookhan gave birth to a son who had special needs. Despite the rigours of parenting slowing her pace, she never stopped outpacing her colleague's chemists. She "dry-labbed" samples, which means she made an educated guess as to what they were rather than performing genuine testing. Dookhan never analysed unidentified samples—those without control-card data—because doing so would have required her to make an educated estimate. Additionally, she didn't dry-lab every sample; rather, she tested about one-fifth of them to be safe. However, to maintain her good statistics, she omitted the chemistry and rubber-stamped the police officers' presumptions. She then signed certificates claiming to have conducted the tests, which is as bad. She essentially lied repeatedly because these certificates were used as evidence in court hearings. She started fabricating proof to cover up her deception. She continued to lie on the stand. Dookhan gave 150 times of sworn testimony in court. At this point, her fellow chemists started to show signs of suspicion. They started monitoring Dookhan's time spent using the microscope and prying into her stack of discarded slides; their findings led them to believe that she was a phoney. At about the same time, Dookhan was discovered by bypassing crucial calibration checks on various devices, ostensibly to save time. And to make matters worse, she forged a colleague's initials on some documentation to hide the fact that she had omitted some necessary measures. In the end, Dookhan pleads guilty to 27 counts of perjury, evidence tampering, and obstruction of justice. Her admission also caused havoc in the Massachusetts court system. All of the approximately 36,000 cases that Dookhan had worked on throughout her career were now questionable since she was unable to prove which samples she had dry-labbed and which she had tested. The state government had to set aside \$30 million to cope with the aftermath; according to one legal advocacy group, it would take 16 paralegals an entire year to notify everyone who was affected.

Following a deluge of appeals, Massachusetts courts ultimately overturned 21,587 convictions, making this the greatest such action in American history (K Sam 2021).

Literature Review

The creator of the health technology company Theranos, Elizabeth Holmes, is examined by Ho (2021) on how she created the legitimacy of her blood-testing business. It broadens the scope of Van Leeuwen's legitimation framework's applicability and advances current research on fraudsters' legitimation tactics. Following a careful analysis of 19 interviews with Elizabeth Holmes, it became clear that Holmes mostly employed discursive tactics to justify the corporate goals, projecting a revolutionary and reliable corporate image and promoting herself as a moral and charitable business elite. Stakeholders were fooled by the illusion this deception generated. These discoveries add to our knowledge of Holmes' dishonesty and shed light on how dishonest businesspeople might legitimize their companies. Another study by (Dundes et al. 2019) concluded that, The adoption of a deep voice and other masculine traits by Elizabeth Holmes coincides with her antagonistic behavior and appearance, which denotes female usurpation of conventions. It also concluded that Elizabeth Holmes didn't feel the need to submit to men because she was solely focused on her career. Although she claimed that her actions were motivated by altruistic benefits, her actions were motivated by ambition. She intended to accomplish her aims in a way that would give her power, fortune, and notoriety. Further, a study by (Mallery 2017) made a report that the case that the public's faith in Holmes' fabricated persona as Steve Jobs' successor—rather than hype—was what eventually allowed the Theranos scam to succeed. The proposed new paradigm of "protective ignorance," an application of rational ignorance in the safeguarding of the cultural capital connected to Jobs' image, is used to explain the origin of this trust. In the context of the Theranos case, the strength of protective ignorance is examined, and recommendations are made to reduce its bad effects in the future without limiting its more beneficial applications. A study by (Driscoll, 2014) critically

examined the Dookhan scandal. The study looked into the shortcomings of the justice system, the Melendez Dias, the need to retest chemical evidence, and the mistakes and nature of Annie Dookhan, aiming to understand how Annie Dookhan went undetected and her motivation to continue frauding the judicial system. With the resources currently available to our office, it has effectively generated a whole new county’s worth of cases, according to Jake Wark, a spokesman for Suffolk County district attorney Daniel F. Conley. A study by David E. Meier, Special Counsel to the Governor’s Office, is attempting to map all the individuals affected by the actions of Annie Dookhan. Further a study asserts that the first suspects were released in September, and a grand jury indicted Ms. Dookhan in December on 27 counts, including tampering with evidence and obstructing the course of justice. 42,000 cases had to be reworked as a result of her arrest. a significant wastage of judicial time and resources.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are:

- To understand what influenced E. Holmes and A. Dookhan to fraud people from the perspective of the sample.
- To identify the attitude of pre-service and in-service facilitators and educationalists towards today’s education-fortifying values.
- To establish shortcomings in today’s education system from the facilitators’ perspective.

Hypothesis

- H1: Student-teachers feel that education failed in inculcating the right values in Elizabeth Holmes and Annie Dookhan.

- H2: In-service teachers feel that education failed in inculcating the right values in Elizabeth Holmes and Annie Dookhan.

Research Methodology

Sample Space of the Study

The study was directed at student-teachers pursuing various teacher education programs at the Regional Institute of Education-NCERT, Mysuru and at In-service teachers from Railway School and VSSC who were attending In-service CPD training at RIE Mysuru. The total sample size was 158. The consent of the participants to use the supplied data for the purposes of the study was requested beforehand. Convenience sampling was employed to choose the participants. Convenience sampling is a technique where the researcher uses people who voluntarily or willingly respond to the questionnaire (Ataş Akdemir & Ayık, 2021; Efe, 2002; Efe, 2008; Efe, 2009; Langham, 2007; Özyurt, 2021).

Procedure and Statistical Analysis

The items in the questionnaire were face validated and then sent for content validation. The questionnaire was pilot-tested on a group of student-teachers. It was then administered to the intended sample through electronic means. The questionnaire had 26 items which included close-ended questions and open-ended questions. The data was collected on spreadsheets and frequency of each response was calculated and indexed to percentage value. The open-ended questions were run through SPSS to find keywords followed by frequency mapping and percentage expression. Thematic analysis was used for the last item on the questionnaire.

Results and Discussion

**Table 1 Student-Teacher Responses: Total Responses(ΣN) = 81
Evaluation of Emotion Trend**

Sl. No	Item	Positive Emotions		Neutral Emotions		Negative Emotions	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
01.	Inner emotions before seeing the video	26	32.09	45	55.5	10	12.3
02.	Inner emotions after seeing the video	03	3.7	40	49.3	38	46.9

Table 2 Close-Ended Questions

S. No	Item	Positive response		Neutral Response		Negative Response	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
1	Do you as an individual like to follow their methods of covering their tracks	0	0	08	9.9	73	90.1
2	After witnessing the video, do you suppose that education has failed?	34	41.9	41	50.6	07	8.6
3	Has societal norms played a role in the transformation of the subjects?	34	42.0	43	53.1	04	4.9
4	Do you think that the audience is also a reason for this trail?	33	40.7	36	44.4	12	14.7
5	If they had pleaded guilty, do you think the judicial system should pardon or reduce the punishment?	24	29.6	15	18.5	42	51.9
6	Will punishment will bring about change in their attitude	08	9.9	58	71.6	15	18.5
7	Did you find remorse in any of them?	20	24.6	18	22.2	43	53.0
8	Thinking of consequences will you proceed or drop off from such activities?	67	82.7	09	11.1	05	6.2
9	Is this behavior because the person is craving for recognition and is restless to achieve it by any means?	47	58	30	37	04	4.9
10	If you can't do such an act, will you be envious at that person's courage and guts and the recognition he /she gets in society?	15	18.5	10	12.3	56	69.1
11	Do you think that society per se is prime reason for intelligent students to select this path knowing the risk involved?	23	28.4	41	50.6	17	20.9
12	If such cases are put for discussion or debate, will it help students to introspect their inner self and values?	57	70.4	18	22.2	06	07.4

Table 3 Open-Ended Questions

S. No	Item	Standard Response Range	N	%
1	As an individual, can you judge the subjects? If so, what is your judgement?	No Judgement	23	28.39
		Greedy for Fame	12	14.81
		Unethical	07	08.64
		Wrongdoing	18	22.22
		Punishment	11	13.58
		Inappropriate response	10	12.34
2	What do you think has led them to such activities?	Fame, Money & Greed	48	59.25
		Prove themselves	05	06.17
		Childhood / Family	17	20.98
		Lacking Morality	05	06.17
		Inappropriate response	06	07.40
3	Did education do its part in imparting values? justify.	Yes	25	30.86
		Maybe	09	11.11
		No	32	39.50
		Values are above education	15	18.51
4	Do you define their trajectory as a successful one? if so, on what front are you classifying success?	Yes, Made money	06	07.40
		Success is constructive	12	14.81
		No, Wrong path	55	67.90
		Success is subjective	06	07.40
		Inappropriate	03	03.70

5	Imagine yourself in her position, what would you do? and why?	Neutral	11	13.58
		Same as the subjects	02	02.46
		Be rightful	12	14.81
		Not deceive	20	24.69
		Regret/ Confess/ Plead guilty	28	34.56
6	Academically strong, what must have motivated them to select easy path for glory?	Escape	08	09.87
		Greed/ Money/ Short success	33	40.74
		Bringing up/ Environment	11	13.58
		Failed rightfulness	11	13.58
		Interest/ deceit	06	07.40
		Over-confidence	05	06.17
		Recognition	09	11.11
7	Have you ever thought of easy ways to achieve your goal? If so, did you think of the consequences?	Neutral response	06	07.40
		No easy ways	36	44.44
		Yes, Dropped	19	23.45
		Yes, proceeded	10	12.34
8	Having all opportunities to take up this path, you may not take up, why?	Inappropriate response	02	02.46
		Consequence, Fear / Guilt	21	25.92
		Harmful, Unlawful	14	17.28
		Hardworking	04	04.93
		Morals, Values	25	30.86
		Disinterest, Better off	15	18.51
		I Might	01	01.23
9	Should education highlight such case? If yes, how would this exposure effect the student? if no, why not?	Don't Know	01	01.23
		Yes, Understand consequences	19	23.45
		Yes, Awareness	29	35.80
		No, Can incite same actions	08	09.87
		Yes, Use to teach values	07	08.64
		Depends on student	11	13.58
10	Which would be your choice and why? A. "Be satisfied with what you got and keep striving hard to achieve your goal in a rightful way" or B, "adapt any means to achieve your set goal".	Inappropriate response	07	08.64
		A, Satisfaction, Rightful	70	86.41
		A, Hard work	09	11.11
		B	0	0
11	Do you feel that students of this generation are imbued with ethics and values? If NO give suggestions for achieving this aspect to make the world a better place to live.	Inappropriate response	02	02.46
		Yes	14	17.28
		Neutral response	18	22.22
		No, Values and guidance	28	34.56
		No, bringing up change	07	08.64
		No, Awareness incitement	07	08.64
No	07	08.64		

Thematic Analysis

Item 26: What would be your final conclusion?
 “Education should give sight to more importance

to the way we live and why we should be living in a straight and rightful way. Also, education should inculcate students the value of being

self-sufficient, happy, self-care and happy with the what we have.”

“It is equally important to empathize other people in the society and recognize that we have got no rights to hurt others by any means for our own requirements.”

“Education is incomplete without imparting

moral values and love and concern towards its fellow citizens”

“Knowledge can be used both ways it’s you who decides how to use it.”

“One should work hard and follow their paths in right order.”

In-service Teacher Responses

Total Responses($\sum N$) = 77

Table 4 Evaluation of Emotional Trends

S. No	Item	Positive Emotions		Neutral Emotions		Negative Emotions	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
01.	Inner emotions before seeing the video	15	19.4	52	67.5	10	12.9
02.	Inner emotions after seeing the video	02	02.5	36	46.7	39	50.6

Table 5 Close-Ended Questions

Sl. No	Item	Positive response		Neutral Response		Negative Response	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
01.	Do you as an individual like to follow their methods of covering their tracks	09	11.6	10	12.9	58	75.3
02.	After witnessing the video, do you suppose that education has failed?	18	23.3	04	05.1	55	71.4
03.	Has societal norms played a role in the transformation of the subjects?	37	48	33	42.8	07	09
04.	Do you think that the audience is also a reason for this trail?	29	37.6	20	25.9	28	36.3
05.	If they had pleaded guilty, do you think the judicial system should pardon or reduce the punishment?	23	29.8	21	27.2	33	42.8
06.	Will punishment will bring about change in their attitude	25	32.4	39	50.6	13	16.8
07.	Did you find remorse in any of them?	22	28.5	10	12.9	45	58.4
08.	Thinking of consequences will you proceed or drop off from such activities?	49	63.6	10	12.9	18	23.3
09.	Is this behavior because the person is craving for recognition and is restless to achieve it by any means?	55	71.4	15	19.4	07	09
10.	If you can’t do such an act, will you be envious at that person’s courage and guts and the recognition he /she gets in society?	18	23.3	12	15.5	47	61
11.	Do you think that society per see is prime reason for intelligent students to select this path knowing the riskinvolved?	26	33.7	33	42.8	18	23.3
12.	If such cases are put for discussion or debate, will it help students to introspect their inner self and values?	62	80.5	11	14.2	03	3.8

Table 6 Open-Ended Questions

S. No	Item	Response Range	N	%
1	As an individual, can you judge the subjects? If so, what is your judgement?	No Judgement	07	09.09
		Greedy for Fame	15	19.48
		Unethical	22	28.57
		Wrongdoing	12	15.58
		Punishment	21	27.27
		Inappropriate response	0	0
2	What do you think has led them to such activities?	Fame, Money & Greed	28	36.37
		Prove themselves	13	16.88
		Childhood / Family	08	10.38
		Lacking Morality	26	33.76
		Inappropriate response	2	02.59
3	Did education do its part in imparting values? justify.	Yes	19	24.67
		Maybe	26	33.76
		No	29	37.66
		Values are above education	03	03.89
4	Do you define their trajectory as a successful one? if so, on what front are you classifying success?	Yes, Made money	01	01.29
		Success is constructive	09	11.68
		No, Wrong path	59	76.62
		Success is subjective	08	10.38
		Inappropriate	0	0
5	Imagine yourself in her position, what would you do? and why?	Neutral	12	15.58
		Same as the subjects	01	01.29
		Be rightful	08	10.38
		Not deceive	48	62.33
		Regret/ Confess/ Plead guilty	07	09.09
		Escape	01	01.29
6	Academically strong, what must have motivated them to select easy path for glory?	Greed/ Money/ Short success	29	37.66
		Bringing up/ Environment	11	14.2
		Failed rightfulness	09	11.68
		Interest/ deceit	12	15.58
		Over-confidence	09	11.68
		Recognition	06	07.79
		Neutral response	01	01.29
7	Have you ever thought of easy ways to achieve your goal? If so, did you think of the consequences?	No easy ways	47	61.03
		Yes, Dropped	25	32.46
		Yes, proceeded	04	05.19
		Inappropriate response	01	01.29

8	Having all opportunities to take up this path, you may not take up, why?	Consequence, Fear / Guilt	27	35.06
		Harmful, Unlawful	14	18.18
		Hardworking	04	05.19
		Morals, Values	19	24.67
		Disinterest, Better off	12	15.58
		I Might	01	01.29
		Don't Know	0	0
9	Should education highlight such case? If yes, how would this exposure effect the student? if no, why not?	Yes, Understand consequences	26	33.76
		Yes, Awareness	31	40.25
		No, Can incite same actions	08	10.38
		Yes, Use to teach values	03	03.89
		Depends on student	06	07.79
		Inappropriate response	01	01.29
10	Which would be your choice and why? A. "Be satisfied with what you got and keep striving hard to achieve your goal in a rightful way" or B, "adapt any means to achieve your set goal".	A, Satisfaction, Rightful	59	76.62
		A, Hard work	17	22.07
		B	0	0
		Inappropriate response	01	01.29
11	Do you feel that students of this generation are imbibed with ethics and values? If NO give suggestions for achieving this aspect to make the world a better place to live.	Yes	13	16.88
		Neutral response	17	22.07
		No, Values and guidance	31	40.25
		No, bringing up change	08	10.38
		No, Awareness incitement	07	09.09
		No	01	01.29

Thematic Analysis

Item 26: What would be your final conclusion?

“Education plays most important role in shaping a ‘PERSONS’s’ personality. It treats ignorance with knowledge, Modifies inability into ability , filters immoralities and installs sense of ethics... etc. So, present day education needs to be modified in several angles to bring out the real goal of education”

“I would conclude that there should be improvement made upon current education system in my view on imparting values into young. Teachers who are getting employed with full passion in their field can help build better citizens for tomorrow if they get enough support by law and society can they bring about a change in present society making world a better place to live in.”

“Human Behaviour is unpredictable, just because a person is educated, doesn't mean they are having a good work ethic. Situations make them who they are as a person, but education also

does play a role. My take away from all this that, success that is achieved the easy or the crooked way is short lived and values are essentially what makes us humans and it is crucial that we hold on to them.”

“Academic excellence alone cannot be considered as a proper measurement of an individual. Their ethical and moral values should be analyzed as well. Achieving goal shouldn't focus only on the end product, the path or the process should also be considered.”

The emotional trend in the student-teachers remained neutral before the video but there was a short spike in negative emotions and a fall in positive emotions after witnessing the videos. Majority do not wish to follow the path chosen by the subjects, considering the consequences. The data suggests that the sample is neutral towards punishment bearing reformation in the subjects. They do agree that the subjects crave recognition and greed and that fueled their actions. The majority of student-teachers feel that education has failed and has also

gone down without inculcating values. Over 70% of the sample asserted that discussing such ethical cases in the classroom will help children distinguish right over wrong and evaluate their actions, considering consequences. They reiterated that education is incomplete without imparting moral values and love and concern towards its fellow citizens should inculcate students the value of being self-sufficient, happy, self-care and happy with the what we have.

The emotional trend in the in-service teachers before the video was majority neutral and there was a short spike in negative emotions after the videos. The majority of in-service teachers do not wish to follow the path trodden by Elizabeth Holmes and Annie Dookhan and over 70% of the sample assert that the subjects' craving for recognition and restlessness to achieve something has led them down the fraudulent path. The teachers do not think that education failed completely but do agree that education has failed in inculcating values. They asserted that society and the audience played a major role in aiding the acts of E. Holmes and A. Dookhan. They believe that punishment can bring about some reform in the subjects. Over 80% of the sample asserted that discussing such ethical cases in the classroom will help children distinguish right over wrong and evaluate their actions, considering consequences. They also reiterated that education and ethics must go hand-in hand and that there should be improvement made upon current education system on imparting values into young children.

Conclusion

Both student teachers and In-service teachers had a spike of negative emotions after witnessing the cases of E. Holmes and A. Dookhan. Both the samples were pretty clear that they condemned the actions of the subjects and wish that they never attempt such a path. Both student-teachers and in-service teachers felt the lack of value-oriented education and stressed on the need for values alongside conceptual knowledge. They deemed that educating students with such ethical cases would create awareness and help students develop their moral compass.

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Annexure

Graph 1

Graph 2

Graph 3

Graph 4

Graph 5

Graph 6

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